

SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELL (SLAC) IMPLEMENTATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AMONG ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 3

Pages: 253-265

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1959

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12536356

Manuscript Accepted: 05-23-2024

School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Implementation and its Impact on the Personal and Professional Development among Elementary Teachers

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the impact of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation on the professional and personal development among elementary teachers. Descriptive-correlational research design and complete enumeration technique were used. Findings reveal that elementary teachers generally have agreed that SLAC implementation was extensive in terms of learner diversity, content and pedagogy, content assessment and reporting, 21st century skills and ICT integration and curriculum contextualization. They also concurred that the implementation of SLAC had a profound influence on their professional and personal development. However, the perceived impact on teachers when grouped according to the number of years was statistically insignificant. A notable disparity in the perceived impact of teachers on their personal growth when grouped according to sex was identified. In terms of their professional growth, no significant difference was observed. A significant relationship between the extent of implementation of SLAC and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on personal and professional growth was evident. Recommendations included more SLAC sessions on learner diversity and content assessment. Reporting should be allocated in a gender-sensitive approach. Innovative and interactive strategies in the implementation of SLAC must be utilized to intensify its impact on the personal and professional growth of teachers.

Keywords: *school learning action cell, professional growth, personal growth*

Introduction

The quality of learning is greatly influenced by the quality of teaching. The good personality traits and quality of teachers are vital factors to be considered in developing holistic learners who are value-driven, qualified with 21st-century skills, and capable of driving the country toward development and progress. Indeed, teachers' performance has a significant relation to students' achievement (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019).

Evidence suggests that teachers' work within this framework, especially in the United States, reinforces the delivery of quality instruction which may lead to the improvement of student achievement (Lomos et al., 2011; Jones et al., 2013) and contribute to the effectiveness of schools' performances and services (Louis et al., 2010; Hofman et al., 2015).

In the Philippines there are lot of problems in the implementation of the SLAC session. The problems included some teachers who were not ICT knowledgeable and the difficulty in scheduling due to many school activities (Vega, 2020; Reazo, 2017). Further, contractual and fixed time for teacher collaboration and also for instructional leadership were not enough due to many duties or additional tasks; hence, teachers had no or lacked time for all (Antinluoma et al., 2021).

In the districts of Aleosan where the researcher is affiliated, not all schools implementing the SLAC get tracked and assessed regularly. In addition, SLAC implementation has just been established anew in some schools. As observed by the researcher on SLAC implementation among schools in Aleosan, teachers' lack of awareness and knowledge of their roles limit their level of participation in the activity, depriving them of harnessing their full potential and supporting their continuing professional development through the conduct of SLAC activities.

Cognizant of the lack of monitoring of the SLAC sessions, personnel's limited grasp of the processes, and the host of other technical problems in implementing the SLAC in schools, the researcher is prompted to undertake the study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perceived impact of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) implementation on the professional and personal development among teachers at elementary schools in the West and East Districts of Aleosan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, qualification, and teaching experience in years when SLAC is implemented?
2. How extensive is the implementation of SLAC among teachers in the areas of:
 - 2.1. learner diversity;
 - 2.2. content and pedagogy;
 - 2.3. content assessment and reporting;
 - 2.4. 21st century skills and ICT integration; and
 - 2.5. curriculum contextualization as rated by the respondents?

3. What is the perceived impact of SLAC implementation in terms of the personal and professional growth of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference on the extent of SLAC implementation in terms of:
 - 4.1. learner diversity;
 - 4.2. content and pedagogy;
 - 4.3. content assessment and reporting;
 - 4.4. 21st century skills and ICT integration; and
 - 4.5. curriculum contextualization when grouped according to selected demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant difference between the perceived impact of SLAC implementation in terms of personal, professional growth of the elementary teachers when grouped according to sex?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of SLAC and perceived impact of SLAC implementation?

Literature Review

School Learning Action Cell (SLAC)

Modern society demands high quality teaching and learning from teachers. Teachers have to possess a great deal of knowledge and skills with regard to both teaching and assessment practices in order to meet those demands and standards of quality education. Effective teacher learning and professional development is important for student achievement. Teacher learning is a continuous process that promotes teachers' teaching skills, master new knowledge, develop new proficiency, which in turn, help improve students' learning (Bandura, 2019).

Learner Diversity

Learner diversity is an issue worth addressing in education practices across countries if inclusive societies are to be developed, promoted and sustained (Possi & Milinga, 2017). Successful teachers know and care for their students. Including learner diversity and student inclusion in the LAC sessions emphasized that learners are the reason for all education processes. It is the central role of teachers to establish learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity. It underscores the importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding of, as well as respect for, learners' characteristics and experiences. Diversity emanates from a variety of factors (which may be in combination) such as gender, community membership, religious beliefs, family configurations, and special learning needs (Binauhan, 2019).

Content and Pedagogy

By studying the K to 12 curriculum, teachers are able to prepare for lessons and are more relaxed in executing lesson plans. They should master content and performance standards and learning competencies so that they can plan lessons, deliver instruction effectively, and assess the learning that results from their teaching. The teachers can collaboratively plan lessons during the LAC and these can be implemented for a specified period of time, after which, teachers can share their experiences on the outcomes of their collaborative lesson plans (Department of Education, 2016)

Content Assessment and Reporting

Assessment is the primary propeller of learning that interfaces between what the teacher expects the students to learn, and the evidence that demonstrates students' learning success and achievement (Northcote et al., 2017).

21st Century Skills and ICT Integration

Bringing 21st-century skills into the teaching and learning situation is a central feature of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Teachers must enrich lessons with simple integration strategies utilizing Information and Communications Technology (ICT) that are developmentally appropriate. Instruction and assessment processes can be made more collaborative with ICT, which teachers can implement with the tools and equipment available in their schools. Deepening curriculum contextualization through indigenization is essential for communities that have cultural practices that are different from the majority of people in the same locality (DepEd Order, 2016, as cited by Mendoza et al., 2017).

Communication skills. Communication is the practice of conveying ideas quickly and clearly. Students need to learn how to communicate effectively. That includes minimizing tangents, speaking directly to an idea, and checking other respondents to make sure they are engaged (Stauffer, 2020). Reading an audience — even if it is just two other people in a group discussion — lets students determine whether they should keep expanding on an idea or wrap up their point. Students practice communication to become better at efficiently conveying an idea without losing their point “in the weeds,” so to speak.

Collaboration skills. Collaboration is the practice of working together to achieve a common goal. Collaboration is important because whether students realize it or not, they will probably work with other people for the rest of their lives. Practicing collaboration and teamwork helps students understand how to address a problem, pitch solutions, and decide the best course of action. It is also helpful for them to learn that other people do not always have the same ideas that they do (Stauffer, 2020).

Critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is the practice of solving problems, among other qualities. In addition to working through problems, solving puzzles, and similar activities, critical thinking also includes an element of skepticism (Stauffer, 2020). With critical thinking, students do not just learn a set of facts or figures. Instead, they learn how to discover the facts and figures for themselves, ask questions, become engaged in the world around them, and eventually help others think critically, too.

Creativity skills. Creativity is related to the production of new and useful ideas on products, services, or processes that are both novel and potentially useful. Because employee's creativity is presented as an imperative for long-term organizational success, it arises as a critical skill for organizations to lead or adapt to change (van Laar et al., 2020).

Curriculum Contextualization

Curriculum implementation and the instructional process are consistent with the learners' academic achievement, but the instructional materials used are not significantly congruous with the latter. The dearth of contextualized IMs, teachers' lack of training, and the resistance towards contextualization impede the full implementation of contextualized curriculum (Cubillas et al., 2021). According to Leite, Fernandes and Figueiredo (2018), teachers are encouraged to contextualize the curriculum in their everyday academic practices to support their pupils' academic achievement and total development.

Perceived Impact of SLAC on Personal Growth of Teachers

Vega (2020) explained on the benefits of SLAC in which four themes emerged from his study: (1) Better Working Environment (2) Develop Good Relationship, (3) Professional Growth, (4) Content and Pedagogical Knowledge. Camaraderie was the most common benefit as experienced by the five schools in the study. Further, Vega revealed that during the FGD teachers expressed that they had fun and enjoyed participating in the SLAC activities. The activity done in the SLAC session created bonding among the teachers and enabled them to create friendship. Furthermore, the topics in SLAC, particularly on Pedagogical Retooling in Mathematics, Language and Science (PRIMALS) which were echoed by the teacher who attended the seminar, empowered them to develop leadership skills and gave them knowledge on the recent pedagogy in teaching.

Perceived Impact of SLAC on the Professional Growth of Teachers

Vega (2020) disclosed that professional development was one of the benefits experienced by science teachers in their implementation of LAC in their schools. Teachers revealed that they experienced test construction, code of ethics, curriculum, and research writing as topics they discussed in their SLAC. They appreciated its significance to the science concept and methods, where trends in science education were discussed like research, robotics, and different terms and policies in DepEd like the use of Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS), Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), and the like.

Task reduction. Teacher responsibilities may be lessened without compromising the quality of instruction. In fact, this strategy offers a viable solution to the 'excessive' yet necessary workload that Filipino teachers are now facing (Tomacruz, 2018).

The second major category extracted from the thematic analysis of the transcribed interview in the study conducted by Bajar et al (2021) is the perceived effect of the SLAC in teaching as a pedagogy. In this category, two subcategories were identified: (1) teacher efficacy and (2) instructional mastery. The respondents stressed that the intervention, in the form of being a professional learning community, allowed them to re-examine their teaching practices and further hone them by adopting to the appropriate teaching approaches as applied in other specialized disciplines.

Instructional mastery. One of the top and persisting concerns in out-of-field teaching is the mastery of both the content and the method of delivering lessons, especially on specialized topics. In their study (Bajar et al, 2021), one teacher re-echoed this concern saying that they may gradually 'learn the method but would certainly find difficulty in the mastery of content.' As a response, teachers were reminded that no topic would be very difficult to grasp with appropriate teaching strategies. As such, they were made to realize that no teaching strategy fits all contexts, and that variation is needed thus the conduct of the SLAC sessions.

Methodology

Research Design

The study uses descriptive-correlational research methods. It employs descriptive design since it describes the demographic profile of the respondents, the extent of implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation among the elementary school teachers of West and East Districts of Aleosan. Also, it utilizes correlational method since it determines the significant difference between the extent of SLAC implementation and the professional and personal growth of the teachers, the significant difference between the impact of SLAC implementation on the professional and personal growth of the elementary teachers as perceived by the respondents when grouped according to selected profile, and the relationship between the extent of the SLAC implementation and the perceived impact of the SLAC implementation to the professional and personal growth of the teachers.

Participants

The study was conducted in the elementary schools of West and East Districts of the municipality of Aleosan. The respondents are composed of 215 teachers who are the teachers of 22 schools in Aleosan West and East Districts for School Year 2022 – 2023.

Complete enumeration was employed in determining the respondents of the study. It means that 215 teachers in the two districts of Aleosan were taken as respondents of the study.

Instruments

A researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather the relevant quantitative data for the study. The contents were primarily based on the readings of related literature and studies which were taken from books, journals, and educational website from the internet. All questions were written in English.

The questionnaire consists of three parts. Part I includes the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II consists of items on the extent of implementation of SLAC in the areas of The Learner Diversity, Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment and Reporting, 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration, and Curriculum Contextualization among the elementary school teachers of the two districts. Part III focuses on the perceived impact of the SLAC implementation on the personal and professional growth of the respondents.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument underwent face and content validation to establish its validity and reliability. Experts in the field investigated the features of the instrument. The instrument was critically examined to ensure clarity of instructions and the objectives of the study were met. The validators checked the language, contents, and the structure of the items. To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher pilot-tested the instrument to 20 non-respondents in Midsayap Pilot Central Elementary School, Midsayap, Cotabato. The Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument with an r-value of .98 indicative of a very reliable instrument.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher asked approval from the Graduate School Dean of Notre Dame of Midsayap College, Division Office, and the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS). After securing the approval, the researcher coordinated with the concerned principals of the schools involved in the study for the smooth administration of the questionnaire. Then, the researcher personally distributed and retrieved the questionnaires. Focus Group Discussion was conducted to substantiate and supplement the data collected. Questions for the Focus Group Discussion were crafted based on the results of the study. After the retrieval of all the questionnaires, the data gathered were coded, were given to the statistician, and were processed through the use of appropriate statistical program.

Data Analysis

This study used appropriate statistical tools to process data. For Problem 1, this was treated using the frequency count and percentage distribution. For Problems 2 and 3, weighted mean and standard deviation were computed. For problems 4 and 5, Kruskal-Wallis test and Mann-Whitney U test were computed to determine the significant difference in the SLAC implementation in terms of Learner Diversity, Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment and Reporting, 21st Century Skills and ICT integration, and Curriculum Contextualization. Finally, Problem 6 which tested the significant relationship between the extent of SLAC implementation and perceived impact, Spearman rho correlation was utilized.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. The data are presented in tabular form and include the profile of the respondents, the extent of the implementation of SLAC in different areas of focus, and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation in terms of the personal and professional growth of the respondents.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to age, sex, educational qualifications, and teaching experiences in years. Based on the findings of the study, most of the respondents belong to the 31-40 years old age group gaining the highest frequency of 73 or 34 % of the respondents, while 68 or 31.60 % of them belong to the 41-50 years old range. Moreover, respondents aging from 61 and above reveal the lowest frequency of 3 or 1.40 %. More female respondents are involved which consists of 189 or 87.90 % of the 215 respondents and only 26 of them or 12.10 % are male.

Table 1 further reveals that 83 or 38.60 % earned their MA units, while 78 or 36.30 % were full-fledged Master's degree holders. Among the 215 respondents, 52 or 24.20 % remains with their Baccalaureate degrees, while only 2 or 0.90 % has earned their Doctoral units. In terms of years of teaching experience, more than half of the respondents or 112 (52.10 %) have taught in the Department of Education for 1-10 years already, while 75 or 34.90 % have been connected with the Department for 11-20 years already. Moreover, there are 5 respondents or 2.30 % who have been serving the Department for 31 years and above.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
24-30	44	20.50
31-40	73	34.00
41-50	68	31.60
51-60	27	12.60
61 and above	3	1.40
Total	215	100.00
Sex		
Male	26	12.10
Female	189	87.90
Total	215	100.00
Educational Qualifications		
Baccalaureate	52	24.20
With MA Units	83	38.60
Master's Degree	78	36.30
With Doctoral Units	2	0.90
Total	215	100.00
Teaching Experiences in Years		
1-10	112	52.10
11-20	75	34.90
21-30	23	10.70
31 and above	5	2.30
Total	215	100.00

Extent of the Implementation of School Learning Action Cell

The extent of the implementation of SLAC in terms of Learner Diversity, Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment and Reporting, 21st Century Skills and ICT integration, and Curriculum Contextualization are displayed in Tables 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, and 2.5.

Table 2.1. Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in terms of Learner Diversity

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...				
1. include learner diversity as a topic for discussion in the session.	4.35	.58	Agree	Extensive
2. deepen my understanding of learner diversity in class.	4.32	.59	Agree	Extensive
3. establish a learning environment that is responsive to learners' diversity.	4.29	.62	Agree	Extensive
4. understand the learner's characteristics and experiences.	4.30	.57	Agree	Extensive
5. discuss that diversity emanates from a variety of factors such as gender, affiliations, religious beliefs, family configurations, and special learning needs.	4.21	.60	Agree	Extensive
6. celebrate diversity in the classroom (like Christmas, Ramadan, fasting and prayer).	4.25	.66	Agree	Extensive
7. employ differentiated instruction that will address the diverse needs of the learners.	4.37	.60	Agree	Extensive
8. respect diversity to foster harmony in the class.	4.37	.63	Agree	Extensive
9. prepare materials for remedial instruction to address learning difficulties.	4.39	.62	Agree	Extensive
10. develop caring attitudes toward learners.	4.50	.56	Strong	Very Extensive
Overall Mean	4.34	.60	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

Table 2.1 shows the results of the extent of implementation of SLAC in terms of Learner Diversity. As shown in Table 2.1, item 10 which states that the school learning action cell in our school helps to develop caring attitudes toward learners got the highest mean of 4.50 described as Strongly Agree with an interpretation of Very Extensive and a standard deviation of 0.56.

Furthermore, item 9, which states that the learning action cell in our school helps to prepare materials for remedial instruction to address learning difficulties, obtained the second highest mean of 4.39 and a standard deviation of 0.62 interpreted as Extensive, followed by items 8 and 7, respect diversity to foster harmony in the class, and employ differentiated instruction that will address the diverse needs of the learners have a weighted mean of 4.37 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with standard deviation of .63 and .60, respectively.

Moreover, item 7 which indicates respect diversity to foster harmony in the class shared the same as the third highest mean of 4.37 and a standard deviation of 0.63 interpreted as Extensive with item 8 which states employ differentiated instruction that will address the diverse needs of the learners with a standard deviation of 0.60 interpreted as Extensive.

On the other hand, items 5 and 6 which state that the Learning action cell in our school helps me discuss that diversity emanates from

a variety of factors such as gender, affiliations, religious beliefs, family configurations, and special learning needs (M=4.21, sd= .60) and celebrate diversity in the classroom like Christmas, Ramadan, fasting and Prayer (M=4.25, sd= .66) obtained the lowest mean with a description of Agree interpreted as Extensive.

The overall mean revealed that in terms of Learner Diversity, the respondents agree that the SLAC implementation was Extensive as evidenced by the mean of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.60.

Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Content and Pedagogy

Table 2.2 shows the extent of the implementation of SLAC in terms of Content and Pedagogy.

Table 2.2. *Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Content and Pedagogy*

Items	Mean Deviation	Standard	Description	Interpretation
The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...				
1. study and analyze the K to 12 Curriculum.	4.24	.67	Agree	Extensive
2. craft jointly and collaboratively my learning goals.	4.21	.60	Agree	Extensive
3. prepare my lessons and be more relaxed in executing my learning lesson plans.	4.27	.61	Agree	Extensive
4. implement developmentally-appropriate teaching methods that respect the individual differences of learners.	4.36	.59	Agree	Extensive
5. master content and performance standards and learning competencies.	4.32	.61	Agree	Extensive
6. plan lessons and deliver instructions effectively.	4.45	.63	Agree	Extensive
7. assess the learning as a result of teaching/instruction.	4.41	.62	Agree	Extensive
8. plan weekly lessons which can be implemented for a specified period of time.	4.36	.61	Agree	Extensive
9. share my experiences to improve subsequent lessons.	4.29	.61	Agree	Extensive
10. translate curriculum content into relevant learning activities.	4.26	.62	Agree	Extensive
Overall Mean and Standard Deviation	4.32	.62	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

Reflected in Table 2.2, item 6 which states that the learning action cell helps me plan lessons and deliver instructions effectively earned the highest mean of 4.45 described as Agree interpreted as Extensive with a standard deviation of 0.63. Item 7 on assess the learning as a result of teaching/instruction came next with the second highest mean of 4.41 interpreted as Extensive and with a standard deviation of 0.62.

Third in the list of indicators with the same mean were items 8 and 4 which states that the learning action cell in our school helps me to plan weekly lessons which can be implemented for a specified period of time and implement developmentally-appropriate teaching methods that respect the individual differences of learners. They both earned a mean of 4.36 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with a standard deviation of 0.61 and 0.59, respectively.

Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of of Content Assessment and Reporting

Table 2.3 shows the extent of the of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Content Assessment and Reporting.

Table 2.3. *Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Content Assessment and Reporting*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...				
1. implement the learner-centered assessment policies.	4.29	.62	Agree	Extensive
2. design assessments of learning in my class.	4.33	.55	Agree	Extensive
3. discuss how data from formative assessment can improve subsequent lessons.	4.27	.58	Agree	Extensive
4. select, organize, and use sound assessment continually.	4.20	.59	Agree	Extensive
5. set a target for desired learning progress for my class.	4.29	.59	Agree	Extensive
6. design means to provide parents with necessary feedback about their children's learning outcomes.	4.28	.63	Agree	Extensive
7. plan and give appropriate feedback to student's academic performance so they can take charge of their learning.	4.32	.63	Agree	Extensive
8. communicate to parents about the performance of their children specifically their strengths and the areas that need to be improved.	4.37	.61	Agree	Extensive
9. report strengths, areas for improvement, and/or where students need to be further assisted or extended.	4.36	.60	Agree	Extensive
10. utilize information from reporting and feedbacking to improve assessment.	4.28	.63	Agree	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.30	.60	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

Obtaining the highest means of 4.37, 4.36 and 4.33 are items 8, 9 and 2 which state that the learning action cell in our school helps me to communicate to parents on the performance of their children specifically their strength and the areas that need to be improved, report strengths, areas for improvement and/or where students need to be further assisted or extended, and design assessments of learning in my class described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with a standard deviations of 0.61, 0.60, and 0.55 respectively.

Meanwhile, items 3 and 4 states that the learning action cell in our school helps me to discuss how data from formative assessment can improve subsequent lessons (M=4.27, sd=.58) and select, organize and use sound assessment continually (M=4.20, sd=.59) obtained the lowest means with a description of Agree and interpreted as Extensive.

Finally, the data reveal that the respondents agreed to have extensively implemented the programs and activities particularly on Content Assessment and Reporting during SLAC session in their schools as evidenced by the overall mean of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.60.

Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration

Table 2.4 shows the extent of implementation of SLAC in terms of 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration.

Table 2.4. *Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration*

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
<i>The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...</i>				
1. communicate with others to become better and efficiently convey my idea without losing my point.	4.34	.59	Agree	Extensive
2. collaborate with other teachers in accomplishing my task.	4.41	.59	Agree	Extensive
3. devise innovative ways of presenting tasks and ideas.	4.27	.64	Agree	Extensive
4. create or try new things which I have not tried before.	4.29	.69	Agree	Extensive
5. strategize techniques or ways in providing solutions to challenges in my classroom or at school.	4.27	.62	Agree	Extensive
6. produce new and useful ideas on products, services, or processes that are both novel and potentially useful.	4.28	.64	Agree	Extensive
7. greatly improve my class presentation ability through ICT.	4.40	.68	Agree	Extensive
8. acquire knowledge on modern instructional materials and teaching techniques.	4.39	.64	Agree	Extensive
9. enrich my lesson content through supplemental Information from the internet.	4.35	.65	Agree	Extensive
10. innovate learning resources that lead me to think reflectively and judge skillfully in deciding relevant information or communication for a given context.	4.24	.65	Agree	Extensive
Overall Mean and SD	4.32	.64	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

The findings reveal that item 2 which states the learning action cell in our school helps me to collaborate with other teachers in accomplishing my task obtained the highest mean of 4.41 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive and with a standard deviation of 0.59. The respondents also agreed on item 7 stating the learning action cell in our school improve greatly my class presentation ability through ICT with the second highest mean of 4.40 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive and with a standard deviation of 0.68.

Emerging as the item with the third highest mean is item 8, stating the learning action cell in our school helped me to acquire knowledge on modern instructional materials and teaching techniques with a mean of 4.39 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with standard deviation of 0.64.

In the study, there were two occurrences of a low mean, the items 3 and 5 on the learning action cell helped me to devise innovative ways of presenting tasks and ideas and strategize techniques or ways in providing solutions to challenges in my classroom or at school obtained the same lowest mean of 4.27 and are both described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with a standard deviation of 0.62 and 0.64, respectively.

Appearing with the lowest mean of 4.24 is item 10 indicating innovate learning resources that lead me to think reflectively and judge skillfully in deciding relevant information or communication for a given context with a standard deviation of 0.65 interpreted as Extensive.

Generally, the data reveal that the implementation of SLAC in terms of 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration is described as Agree by the respondents with an interpretation as Extensive with an overall mean of 4.32 and with a standard deviation of 0.64.

Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Curriculum Contextualization

Table 2.5 presents the extent of the implementation of SLAC in terms of Curriculum Contextualization.

Table 2.5. *Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell in Terms of Curriculum Contextualization*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...				
1. match the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to the diverse needs of learners.	4.27	.64	Agree	Extensive
2. identify and respond to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspiration of the wider school community and other key stakeholders.	4.20	.63	Agree	Extensive
3. link new content to the local experiences that are familiar to learners to make learning more efficient and relevant.	4.21	.65	Agree	Extensive
4. modify lesson guides and learning materials to accommodate the unique contexts of a particular locality.	4.18	.63	Agree	Extensive
5. prepare curricula materials suited to the cultural and social context in which I teach.	4.15	.64	Agree	Extensive
6. recognize that the K to 12 Curriculum is learner-centered, inclusive, and research-based.	4.27	.63	Agree	Extensive
7. realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT-based and global.	4.27	.66	Agree	Extensive
8. engage the community in indigenization processes to make the curriculum is accurate and faithful to their culture.	4.20	.63	Agree	Extensive
9. inculcate that the K to 12 Curriculum is culture responsive and culture-sensitive, integrative and contextualized, relevant and responsive.	4.25	.68	Agree	Extensive
10. work towards an implementation of a curriculum that is competence-based, seamless, and decongested.	4.24	.61	Agree	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.22	.64	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

In terms of Curriculum Contextualization, data reveal that item 1 the learning action cell in our school helps me to match the curriculum content and instructional strategies relevant to the diverse needs of learners shared the same highest mean of 4.27 with a standard deviation of 0.64 with item 6 on recognize that the K to 12 Curriculum is learner-centered, inclusive, and research-based with a standard deviation of 0.63 and item 7 on realize that the K to 12 Curriculum is flexible, ICT-based and global with a standard deviation of 0.66. All three items are described Agree and interpreted as Extensive.

However, items 8 and 2 state that learning action cell in our school helps me engage the community in indigenization processes to make the curriculum accurate and faithful to their culture and identify and respond to opportunities to link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests, and aspiration of the wider school community and other key stakeholders both obtained the lowest mean of 4.20 described as Agree and interpreted as Extensively implemented with a standard deviation of 0.63.

Summary of the Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell

Table 2.6 shows the summary of the extent of implementation of SLAC in terms of Learner Diversity, Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment and Reporting, 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration, and Curriculum Contextualization.

Table 2.6. *Summary of Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell*

Areas	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
1. Learner Diversity	4.34	.60	Agree	Extensive
2. Content and Pedagogy	4.32	.62	Agree	Extensive
3. Content Assessment and Reporting	4.30	.60	Agree	Extensive
4. 21 st Century Skills and ICT Integration	4.32	.64	Agree	Extensive
5. Curriculum Contextualization	4.22	.64	Agree	Extensive
Overall Mean and SD	4.30	.62	Agree	Extensive

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Extensive; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Extensive; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderately Extensive; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Extent; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Extensive at All

As presented in Table 2f, Learner Diversity topped the list of areas considered by the respondents in their implementation of SLAC with a mean of 4.34 with a description of Agree and interpreted as Extensive and with a standard deviation of 0.60. Content and Pedagogy came very closely with 21st Century Skills and Integration which both earned a mean of 4.32 and a standard deviation of 0.62 and 0.64, respectively. The respondents Agreed that the two areas were Extensively implemented.

However, Curriculum Contextualization has the lowest mean of 4.22, described as Agree and interpreted as Extensive with a standard deviation of 0.46. Overall, data reveal that the respondents Agreed that SLAC program and activities in all areas were considered

Extensively implemented as evidenced by the overall mean of 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.62.

Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Personal and Professional Growth

Table 3.1 presents the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on the personal growth of the respondents.

Table 3.1. *Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Personal Growth*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
1. The school learning action cell in our school helps me to... motivate myself to look for opportunities for personal growth.	4.63	.56	Strongly Agree	Very Strong Impact
2. provide venues to enhance my physical and outward appearance.	4.38	.61	Agree	Strong Impact
3. innovate myself to boost my personality.	4.54	.61	Strongly Agree	Very Strong Impact
4. acknowledge others' worth and show appreciation to them.	4.52	.60	Strongly Agree	Very Strong Impact
5. set goals for my personality development.	4.49	.62	Agree	Strong Impact
6. collaborate with colleagues in planning and executing Programs, Projects, and Activities (PPAs).	4.42	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
7. consistently give my best, especially at school.	4.51	.61	Strongly Agree	Very Strong Impact
8. plan for my personal enhancement activities.	4.42	.65	Agree	Strong Impact
9. boost my self-confidence.	4.47	.65	Agree	Strong Impact
10. accept others' criticisms and compliments graciously.	4.42	.63	Agree	Strong Impact
Overall Mean and SD	4.48	.61	Agree	Strong Impact

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Strong Impact; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Strong Impact; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderate Impact; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Impact; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Impact at All

As shown in Table 3.1 items 1, 3 and 4 got the highest means described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Very Strong Impact. These items state that the learning action cell in school helps to motivate myself to look for opportunities for personal growth (M=4.63, sd=.56), innovate myself to boost my personality (M=4.54, sd= .61), and acknowledge others' worth and show appreciation to them (M= 4.52, sd= 0.60).

Nevertheless, items 2 and 8 obtained the low mean, which state that learning action cell in school helps me to provide venues to enhance my physical and outward appearance, gained the mean of 4.38 and plan for my personal enhancement activities earned the mean of 4.42 and both are described as Agree and interpreted as Strong Impact with a standard deviation of 0.61 and 0.65 respectively. Overall, the respondents Agreed that the SLAC implementation had a Strong Impact on their personal growth with a mean of 4.48 and a standard deviation of 0.61.

Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Professional Growth

Table 3.2 presents the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on the professional growth of the respondents.

Table 3.2. *Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Professional Growth*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
The school learning action cell in our school helps me to...				
1. collaborate freely where my administrator and I can ask questions, exchange ideas, and offer suggestions for improvement.	4.44	.58	Agree	Strong Impact
2. encourage others' participation to various professional development workshops or conferences, including SLAC.	4.41	.60	Agree	Strong Impact
3. engage myself in professional discussions inside and outside the school.	4.41	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
4. enable myself to perform at the peak of my abilities.	4.38	.64	Agree	Strong Impact
5. benchmark on quality work and best practices.	4.36	.65	Agree	Strong Impact
6. set my professional goals and objectives.	4.45	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
7. recognize my strengths and weaknesses thereby enhance and improve my professional traits.	4.49	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
8. respect others' point of view and remain very reasonable when I find myself in situations that do not favor my personal beliefs.	4.46	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
9. apply research to my own practice.	4.18	.66	Agree	Strong Impact
10. explore on a variety of activities designed to build my technological comfort and competence.	4.31	.59	Agree	Strong Impact
Overall Mean and SD	4.39	.61	Agree	Strong Impact

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Strong Impact; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Strong Impact; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderate Impact; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Impact; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Impact at All

Interpreted as Strong Impact, item 7, the learning action cell in school helps to recognize my strengths and weaknesses thereby enhance and improve my professional traits emerged with the highest mean of 4.49 with a standard deviation of 0.59. Similarly, items 8 and 6 are rated Agree and interpreted Strong Impact. These items state that the learning action cell in school helps to respect others' point of view and remain very reasonable when I find myself in situations that do not favor my personal beliefs with a mean of 4.46, a standard deviation of 0.59, and set my professional goals and SSS objectives with a mean of 4.45 and a standard deviation of 0.59.

On the contrary, ranked as low are items 10 and 9, which state that SLAC of my school helps me to explore a variety of activities designed to build my technological comfort and competence (M= 4.31, sd= 0.59), and apply research to my own practice (M= 4.18, sd= 0.66) described as Agree interpreted as Strong Impact. Overall, the respondents Agreed that the SLAC implementation created a Strong Impact on their professional growth as evidenced by the overall mean of 4.39 and a standard deviation of 0.61.

Summary of the Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Personal and Professional Growth

Table 3.3 displays the summary of the Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation on the Personal and Professional Growth of the respondents.

Table 3.3. *Summary of the Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on the Personal and Professional Growth*

Areas	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description	Interpretation
1. Personal Growth	4.34	.60	Agree	Strong Impact
2. Professional Growth	4.32	.62	Agree	Strong Impact
Grand Mean and SD	4.33	.61	Agree	Strong Impact

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree/Very Strong Impact; 3.50-4.49, Agree/Strong Impact; 2.50-3.49, Fairly Agree/Moderate Impact; 1.50-2.49, Disagree/A little Impact; 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree/Not Impact at All

Table 3.3 reveals that personal growth obtained a higher mean of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.60 compared to professional growth with a mean of 4.32 and a standard deviation of 0.62. As perceived by the respondents, they Agreed that SLAC implementation created a Strong Impact in both areas. Generally, SLAC implementation had a Strong Impact on the personal and professional growth of the respondents as indicated by the overall mean of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.61.

Difference on the Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell When Grouped According to Number of Years in Service

Table 4 shows the difference in the perceived impact of SLAC implementation when grouped according to number of years in service.

Table 4. *Difference on the Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell When Grouped According to Number of Years in Service*

Areas	Length of Service	N	Mean Rank	z-value	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Learner Diversity	1-10	112	17.40	.851	3	.837	NS	Do Not Reject H ₀₁
	11-20	75	14.88					
	21-30	23	14.58					
	31 and above	5	18.17					
	Total	215						
Content and Pedagogy	1-10	112	16.80	.995	3	.803	NS	Do Not Reject H ₀₁
	11-20	75	12.63					
	21-30	23	17.50					
	31 and above	5	17.86					
	Total	215						
Content Assessment and Reporting	1-10	112	14.60	.395	3	.941	NS	Do Not Reject H ₀₁
	11-20	75	18.13					
	21-30	23	17.50					
	31 and above	5	17.25					
	Total	215						
21 st Century Skills and ICT Integration	1-10	112	18.20	1.891	3	.595	NS	Do Not Reject H ₀₁
	11-20	75	11.00					
	21-30	23	18.75					
	31 and above	5	17.42					
	Total	215						
Curriculum Contextualization	1-10	112	11.10	4.282	3	.233	NS	Do Not Reject H ₀₁
	11-20	75	16.50					
	21-30	23	13.58					
	31 and above	5	19.89					
	Total	215						

Results revealed that there is no significant difference between the perceived impact of SLAC when grouped according to length of service. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the extent of SLAC implementation in terms of the Learner Diversity, Content and Pedagogy, Content Assessment and Reporting, 21st Century Skills and ICT integration, and Curriculum Contextualization when grouped according to years in service is not rejected. Since the p-values .837, .803, .941, .595, and .233 are all greater than the .050 level of significance.

Difference in the Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell When Grouped According to Sex

Table 5 shows the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on personal and professional growth when grouped according to sex.

Table 5. *Perceived Impact School Learning Action Cell When Grouped According to Sex*

Areas	Sex	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	z-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Personal Growth								
	Male	26	84.96	2209.00	-2.031	.042	Significant	Reject H ₀₂
	Female	189	111.17	21011.00				
	Total	215						
Professional Growth								
	Male	26	88.65	2305.00	-1.701	.089	Not Significant	Do Not Reject H ₀₂
	Female	189	110.66	20915.00				
	Total	215						

Data reveal that there is a significant difference between the perceived impact of SLAC implementation in terms of personal growth of the elementary teachers when grouped according to sex.

Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference of the perceived impact of SLAC on the personal growth of teachers when grouped according to sex is rejected since the p-value .042 is less than the 0.050 level of significance. However, in terms of the professional growth of the respondents, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference of the perceived impact of SLAC on the professional growth of teachers when grouped according to sex is not rejected. Further, it shows that there is no significant difference in the perceived impact of the SLAC implementation in terms of professional growth between the male and female teachers involved in the study.

Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell and Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation in Terms of Personal Growth and Professional Growth

Table 6.1 reflects the relationship between the extent of implementation of SLAC and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on personal growth.

Table 6.1. *Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of SLAC and Perceived Impact of SLAC Implementation on Personal Growth*

Areas	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Learner Diversity	.523**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Content and Pedagogy	.616**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Content Assessment and Reporting	.592**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
21 st Century Skills and ICT Integration	.667**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Curriculum Contextualization	.615**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Findings reveal that there is moderate to strong positive significant relationship between the extent of SLAC implementation and the perceived impact of SLAC on the personal growth. Thus, null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the extent of implementation of SLAC and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on personal growth is rejected since the p-values of .000 in all indicators are lower than the .01 level of significance. Based on the r-values, data disclose that SLAC has a strong positive relationship to the perceive impact of SLAC in terms of personal growth on the three areas namely 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration, Content and Pedagogy, and Curriculum Contextualization with an r-values of .667**, .616** and .615** respectively.

Table 6.2 reflects the significant relationship between the extent of implementation of SLAC and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on professional growth.

Table 6.2. Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of School Learning Action Cell and Perceived Impact of School Learning Action Cell Implementation on Professional Growth

Areas	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Learner Diversity	.511**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Content and Pedagogy	.561**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Content Assessment and Reporting	.558**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
21 st Century Skills and ICT Integration	.622**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃
Curriculum Contextualization	.633**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀₃

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data reveal that there is a moderate to strong positive significant relationship between the extent of the implementation of SLAC and the perceived impact of SLAC implementation on professional growth. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between extent of implementation of SLAC and perceived impact of SLAC on the professional growth of teachers is rejected since the p-value of .000 in all areas are lesser than 0.01 level of significance. The r-values also show that SLAC has strong positive relationship to perceive input of SLAC in terms of professional growth in the areas of Curriculum Contextualization (.633**), and 21st Century Skills and ICT Integration (.622**).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is evident that teachers overwhelmingly support the extensive implementation of School Learning Action Cell (SLAC). They acknowledge the substantial impact of SLAC on both their personal and professional growth. Teachers did not exhibit any variance in their perceptions of the impact of SLAC implementation based on their years of teaching experience.

Interestingly, a significant disparity emerged in the perceived impact of SLAC implementation concerning personal growth when teachers were categorized by sex. In contrast, no notable distinction was observed in terms of professional growth based on gender. These results underscore the importance of considering gender-specific factors in the design and implementation of professional development initiatives like SLAC to ensure equitable support and growth opportunities for all educators.

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